

**ASSESSMENT AND REGULATION OF NOISE CONDITIONS IN
ENSURING THE ECOLOGICAL SAFETY OF TERMIZ CITY AREAS
(In the case of Termez city)**

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Abstract: Due to scientific and technological progress, protecting the population from noise and its effects remains one of the pressing problems of our time.

Key words . Noise Maps , Markets and public places , Termez City, Acoustic monitoring, Traffic jams , Sanitary norms , Noise winner materials , ecological security , international standards .

INTRODUCTION . In the process of urbanization, the increase in the number of vehicles due to population density in Termez city, as well as the development of industrial activities, further aggravates the noise problem. Noise has a great impact not only on human health, but also on the ecological system of cities. Therefore for also Termez city in the regions noise conditions to study , and them assessment and him/her order to plant the issue previously This in the article Termez in the city noise environment analysis to do, and there is situations assessment and him/her reduce measure events according to recommendations cited .

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

Traffic in Germany to the noise against in the fight roads on the edge noise level determination from equipment active used in France and automatic photo and video cameras noise level strong was the car recognizing take , automatic accordingly photo to take and his/her number reading to the ability has noise radars with equipped is , this

system motor transport to the owner fine pay necessity about the letter automatic accordingly sends . Current of the year at the beginning car on the roads noise height measurement tools installation opportunities learning , noise harmful impact for compensation payment legal mechanism current to grow offer made .

Termez in the city noise level main to the sources includes : 1. Means of transport : Within the city car of transport density high that was basic , main roads and at crossroads noise The intensity increases. 2. Stay places and industry activity diarrhea system . Construction works , and small enterprises and markets activity is noisy sources 3. Population to live in the regions social Activities : Household technique from the means wide in scope use and entertainment events .

Noise conditions evaluation to oneself typical methods noise level in the evaluation we are in time at the request of come out without modern from methods use possible :

1.Acoustic monitoring: Termez city of the territory noise level special voice ruler tools using record Measurements following in places done increase must :

Traffic jams observable roads .

Industry regions .

Markets and public places .

2. Noise maps Creation : Termez of the city noise level determination GIS technologies for based on acoustic maps Maps using city in the regions noise intensity and impact circle determination It gets easier .

3. Mathematician Modeling : Transport flows , industry activity and population from the density come out noise level forecast opportunity gives .

The noise order of the place main measures

- Normative documents working Exit : Termez city in the regions noise level according to local standards current to be necessary . Sanitary norms designation and to them strict compliance is required to do .

- Noise reducer technologies Application : Noise winner from materials using acoustic obstacles install . Green zones and tree planting through noise level natural in a way reduce

- Transport flows Management : Public from transport use promote to do and his/her quality and convenience Increase in vehicles traffic jam level reduction for the purpose alternative the roads organization to be

- Urbanist Projects : Residential places and industry territories noise from sources known in the distance settlement . Population many collectible in places the noise winner architecture solutions application .

Uzbekistan in the legislation of noise harmful to the effect against fight with related legal relationships order eater special law document there is not . With that together , this industry enough not studied . In particular , the last twenty year during only one research However , this in the field relationship row technician documents with order Including health storage Resolution of the Minister of Education No. 0008-20 dated December 29 , 2020 with stay in places , public in buildings , residents to live in the regions and rest in the zones permission done noise level sanitation rules and standards approved . This rule and in the standards of the day on time looking at the sound as follows maximum to the levels permission Table 1

Table 1

T/r	Building or of the regions names	Day times	Sound pressure levels , dB , average geometric frequencies with octave clauses at frequencies , Hz									Sound levels , L _A and the sound equivalent levels , L _{A eq} , dBA	The sound maximum levels , dBA
			31.5	63	125	250	500	1000	2000	4000	8000		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
1 .	Cafe , restaurant , bar and kitchens food in the halls	-	90	75	66	59	54	50	47	45	43	55	70

2 .	Markets in the areas , shops trade in the halls , airport and of the stations passengers in the halls , household service enterprises acceptance at points	-	93	79	70	63	59	55	53	51	49	60	75
3 .	Hospital , clinic and sanatoriums with directly connected in the regions	from 7 o'clock											
		Up to 23	83	67	57	49	44	40	37	35	33	45	60
4 .	Population living homes , clinics , outpatient clinics , dispensaries , rest to take homes , boarding houses , nursing homes and disabled people for boarding schools , preschools education institutions , school and other training homeland and libraries with directly connected in the regions	from 7 o'clock											
		Up to 23	90	75	66	59	54	50	47	45	43	55	70
		from 11 pm to 7 am	76	59	48	40	34	30	27	25	23	35	50
		from 11 pm to 7 am	83	67	57	49	44	40	37	35	33	45	60

5 .	Hotels , campsites and dormitories buildings with directly connected in the regions	from 7 o'clock											
		Up to 23	93	79	70	63	59	55	53	51	49	60	75
		from 11 pm	86	71	64	54	49	45	42	40	39	50	65
		Up to 7											

Received result : Noise from the source distance change with noise intensity level Termez from vehicles on Islam Karimov Street in the city emerging noise , Green world farmer market , population to live places , Termez state engineering and agrotechnology university training to their rooms happening influence change studied . Table 2

Termez in the city take noise level

Table 2

Object names	Measurement transfer places	Sound permission done level , dBA		Sound measurement transfer from places taken information
		LA eq (equivalent)	LA max (maximum)	
1. Population living houses	Population to live places in the territory	55	70	73
		45	60	67
2. Markets in the regions	Sound from the source 2 m away	60	75	80 109.5
3. airport and of the stations passengers in the halls	Sound to the sources close was traffic light in front of	60	75	76.1 67.2

DISCUSSION

Scientists in my opinion , determined results such noise not only heart to attack tendency appearance to be reason to be counted , maybe his/her to develop impact from doing tree is giving and that's why for transportation noise eliminate to grow for relevant measures acceptance to do necessary . Noise and vibration , if their intensity known from the surface increasing if it goes , professional damage is considered . Noise

with fight for general and personal protection tools is used . Enterprises and their separately workshops other noisy to enterprises relatively right planning and placement big importance has . Production release in the buildings the noise noticeable to reduce the walls and the ceilings sound winner materials with cover through done Equipment various mechanisms in design and during installation devices special to shock absorbers installation , rotating details eccentricity reduce , mutual shock parts to the uninjured replacement and etc. on account of vibration reduce opportunity see necessary .

CONCLUSION

Termez city in the regions taken results this showing standing noise level from the norm high to the pointer has that's why for termite city in the regions ecological security in providing noise level assessment and order to plant important importance has . Noise monitoring and order to plant according to done increaseable measures human health protection to do and city ecological stability to provide service does .

Termez in the city ecological security increase according to recommendations

1. Noise monitoring system on the road put : Special monitoring points through noise level permanent control to do
2. Population aware to make : Noise of the impact negative consequences about information giver propaganda their work take to go
3. International from experience Usage : Termez in the city the noise management according to international standards and advanced technologies implementation to be

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